

conference proceedings

COMENIUS

Bratislava Legal Forum

Vol. 1 (2025)

Burda, Turay (eds.)

FACULTY OF LAW
Comenius University
Bratislava

UNFAIR COMMERCIAL PRACTICES IN DIGITAL AGE¹

Jana Strémy²

Abstract: The spread of digital technologies creates several risk vectors for traders. In this article, the author addresses the issue of unfair commercial practices occurring in the digital space. One such practice is deepfake, which has a high potential to mislead consumers because it presents individuals as saying or doing things they never said or did, which can adversely affect consumers' economic decisions. Deepfakes can create highly convincing manipulated audio-visual content that may falsely portray products, services, or even the identity of the trader. Such fabricated material can spread quickly across online platforms, increasing the likelihood that consumers will rely on misleading or entirely false claims when making purchasing decisions. The situation is particularly alarming for traders that use digital marketing tools, as legal liability is a major issue, especially for consumer-oriented content. Using standard methods in social sciences, the author identifies a correlation between artificial intelligence technologies and unfair practices in order to assess the adequacy of legal regulation.

Key words: unfair commercial practices, artificial intelligence, deepfake, consumer, digital technologies, legal liability.

Introduction

In this new AI era, where the ability of machine to replicate the complexity of human is no more a fragment of science fiction but it is becoming reality day after day. Digital transformation brings entrepreneurs (traders) more possibilities of interaction with consumers. Traders engaged in the consumer-facing platforms and e-commerce have used new technologies (from cookies to machine learning and AI) to track and predict consumer behaviour and influence his choice. According to some authors research shows that our human psychological characteristics can be accurately predicted from their digital footprints e.g. Facebook Likes or Tweets.³ So far

¹ This contribution is funded by the EU NextGenerationEU through the Slovak Republic's Recovery and Resilience Plan as part of the Artificial Intelligence for Legal Professions (AILE) project No. 09105-03-V02-00038.

² Faculty of Law, Comenius University in Bratislava

³ MATZ, Sandra – KOSINSKI, Michal – NAVE, Gideon – STILLWELL, David: Psychological targeting as an effective approach to digital mass persuasion, In: Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A. 114 (48) 12714-12719,